

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-05

Roof rainwater
harvesting and storage
for irrigation

//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Rainwater harvesting (roof catchment)

INPUTS

Roof area and gutters; storage;
basic filtration

OUTPUTS

Stored rainwater for irrigation
(and other non-potable uses)

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 7

CONTEXT & SCALE

Farm-level and community-scale applications where roof surfaces are available (e.g., farm buildings, greenhouses, storage halls); scalable from small tanks to larger tank systems

KEY BENEFITS

Local water supply buffering; reduced pressure on groundwater/surface water sources; reduced runoff; water availability during dry periods; modular/scalable; low-tech, low-cost operation

MAIN CONSTRAINTS

Seasonality; storage space and sizing; contamination from roof surfaces

CATEGORY

Rainwater

//02. WHAT IT IS

Rainwater from roof surfaces (e.g., farm buildings or greenhouses) is collected and stored for later irrigation use. The stored rainwater can be supplied via the irrigation

system to the crops when rainfall is insufficient, helping secure water availability at critical growth stages of the crops.

//03. WHY IT MATTERS

In many agricultural settings, irrigation demand peaks during periods when rainfall is low and water resources are scarce. Roof rainwater harvesting provides an additional, local water source that can reduce dependence on freshwater abstraction and

improve resilience to seasonal drought. This is particularly relevant in summer periods, when rainfall often occurs infrequently but as short, high-intensity events that would otherwise generate rapid runoff and remain largely unused.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

Roof-harvesting systems are designed around three main elements: catchment, conveyance, and storage (with an overflow to the nearby irrigation system). Roof runoff is routed via gutters and pipes into storage, often with simple measures such as debris screens, a first-flush device, and basic filtration to improve water quality. Sizing depends on aspects such as available roof area and expected rainfall, irrigation water

demand and timing (peak months), or possible storage volume and material (plastic, concrete tanks, or ponds). Key design considerations include debris management (leaf screens), first-flush diversion, overflow routing, access for inspection/cleaning, and storage placement relative to irrigation points.

Schematic illustration of a roof rainwater harvesting and storage system © Rovira et al. 2020

//05. HOW IT WORKS

Rainfall is collected from roof surfaces via gutters and downpipes. Before entering storage, runoff may pass through a screen and, where required, a first-flush unit and basic filtration. The first-flush unit diverts the initial, more contaminated roof runoff, while filtration removes remaining debris and suspended solids prior to storage. Rainwater is further stored in tanks for later use. When storage capacity is exceeded, overflow is directed to the irrigation sys-

tem, enabling targeted soil infiltration of excess rainwater.

When irrigation is required, stored rainwater can be supplied to the irrigation system. Depending on site-specific needs and the local regulatory framework, stored rainwater can also be blended with other available water sources and/or fertilizers prior to irrigation.

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

Operation and maintenance are generally simple and based on routine tasks like visual inspections of gutters, screens, filters, and inlets as well as checks for blockages, leaks, and proper overflow functioning typically on a weekly basis or after major rainfall events. On a monthly basis debris is removed from screens and filters, and the tank fittings, valves, and pumps (if present) are inspected.

After periods of intense rainfall, accumulated sediment in pre-filters or settling areas needs to be removed. Monitoring activities may also include basic water quality checks depending on intended use and local legal requirements.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

Microbial or chemical contamination is usually low-risk for most irrigation uses but increases with poor maintenance. Risks include contamination from debris, bird activity or roof materials and blockages/overflow issues.. These are mitigated through appropriate roof materials (concrete, ce-

ramic tiles, galvanized iron sheets), gutter and downpipe materials (PVC or aluminum), screening, first-flush diversion, routine cleaning, covered storage, and appropriate filtration. . Compliance with applicable regulations should be ensured for specific rainwater uses.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

Farms with available roof catchment areas (e.g., barns, halls, greenhouses) and existing irrigation systems seeking a practical and scalable approach to buffer rainfall for irrigation during dry periods. Within the GEORGIA project, rainwater harvesting from roofs is implemented together with BioWAG

on a [pilot site in the Danube Plain](#) (Brashlen village, Ruse region, Northern Bulgaria) [SN2.1], and is also used in pilots in [Northern Serbia](#) (Vojvodina region)[SN3.1] and in [southwest Poland](#) at the Agricultural and Hydrological Observatory (Wroclaw-Swojec).

//09. KEYWORDS

Roof runoff; Rainwater harvesting; Storage tanks; Farm tank storage; Decentralized water supply

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

//10. REFERENCES

1. M.d. Rovira, C. Rovira, and M. Masferrer (2020). Is-Rainwater-Harvesting-a-Solution-for-Water-Access-in-Latin-America-and-the-Caribbean-An-Economic-Analysis-for-Underserved-Households-in-El-Salvador. IDP Interamerican Development Bank. Technica Note 1679. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18235/0002689>.

//11. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

1. E. Gur and D. Spuhler "Rainwater harvesting (rural)" SSWM Fact-sheet. N.A.

Online at: <https://sswm.info/sswm-solutions-bop-markets/affordable-wash-services-and-products/affordable-water-supply/rainwater-harvesting-%28rural%29>

2. RAIN Foundation "RAIN Water Quality Guidelines - Guidelines and practical tools on rainwater quality" Guideline document. 2008. Online at: <https://www.susana.org/knowledge-hub/resources?id=4125>

3. B. Rohling, D. Kostenwein, M. Gairing, A. Al-Mahdawi, E. Schmid, E. Bardou and D. Kaufmann, "Flood Risk in Humanitarian Settlements: Compendium of Mitigation Measures" ETH Zurich. 2023. DOI: 10.3929/ethz-b-00064568.

Online at: https://humanitarian-risk.unhcr.org/images/files/fact-sheets/S09_Rainwater_Harvesting_and_Retention_Basins.pdf

4. WaterAid "Rainwater harvesting" Policy Brief. N.A.

Online at: <https://washmatters.wateraid.org/sites/g/files/jkx-oof256/files/2022-04/Rainwater%20harvesting.pdf>

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